

Systematic Review Protocol:

A Hypothesis-Driven Weight-of-Evidence Analysis to Evaluate Potential Endocrine Activity of Oxybenzone Following Exposure from UV Filters in Humans

Review Team

Dr Susan Borghoff¹, Seneca Fitch¹, Janice Britt¹, Mina Suh¹, Kara Franke¹, Daniele Wikoff¹

¹ToxStrategies, USA

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Consistent with guidance provided by the IOM (2011), the sponsors were given the opportunity to review and provide input on the protocol with the purpose of allowing input on the clarity of research question and the approach.

Disclosure of interests

SB, DW, SF, KF, and GC are employed by ToxStrategies, Inc., which is a consulting firm providing services to private and public organizations on toxicology and risk assessment issues. ToxStrategies received consulting fees for tasks related to topic formulation and protocol development, as well as conduct of the review. None of the authors from ToxStrategies will directly benefit, financially or non-financially, from the conclusions of the SR.

SB has consulted, given presentations to regulatory agencies and at scientific conferences, and published scientific manuscripts regarding disruption in endocrine pathways associated with adverse effects on reproduction and developmental changes, and endocrine related tumors. None of these activities involved oxybenzone.

DW has consulted, given presentations at scientific conferences, and published scientific manuscripts involving systematic review methodologies in toxicology and risk assessment. None of these activities involved oxybenzone.

No authors received personal fees.

Rationale (Context)

Oxybenzone, also known as benzophenone-3 (BP-3), is a common chemical ultraviolet (UV) light filter used in sunscreens and other personal care products. Selected studies and reports have suggested that BP-3 may exhibit endocrine disruptor properties; however, a systematic review and structured assessment according to specific guidelines for evaluating potential endocrine disruption properties for all relevant pathways (estrogen, androgen, testosterone, and steroidogenesis; EATS) has not been conducted.

To analyze the weight of evidence of BP-3 as a potential endocrine disruptor, a systematic review will be carried out. The assessment will be carried out according to the ECHA/EFSA (2018) “*Guidance for the identification of endocrine disruptors in the context of Regulations (EU) No 528/2012 and (EC) No 1107/2009*” with considerations of processes used by the USEPA Endocrine Disruptor Screening Program as well as concepts from OECD Guideline 150. This assessment will be facilitated via systematic review as prescribed in the ECHA/EFSA guidance. Systematic review methodologies will be based on that described by the National Toxicology Program’s Office of Health Assessment and Translation (OHAT, 2015), “*Handbook for conducting a literature-based health assessment using OHAT approach for systematic review and evidence integration.*”

This systematic review will advance the knowledge of the topic relative to existing (Ghazipura et al., 2017; Kim and Choi, 2014; Krause et al., 2012); and ongoing efforts (McClatchey et al., 2017), as differentiated by:

1. Utilization of ED guidance and structured assessment of lines of evidence for EATS relative to the potential for activity as well as plausible modes of action relative to adverse outcomes.
2. Integration of *in vitro* data from the literature as well as compiled databases such as ToxCast/Tox21.
3. Utilization of systematic review methodologies, including study quality/validity tools, unique to toxicological data (including *in vitro* study types).
4. Assessment of ED potential and activity in the context of risk as it relates to oxybenzone exposure via UV filters (i.e., sunscreen).

Review Question (PECO)

Primary question: Does oxybenzone have endocrine disrupting properties in humans under the conditions of use as a UV filter?

Sub-questions, consistent with ECHA/EFSA (2018) guidance:

- Does oxybenzone modulate estrogen, androgen, thyroid, or steroidogenesis pathways?

- Are any observed modalities associated with adverse effect(s) (i.e., are reproductive, developmental, or carcinogenic effects a consequence of an endocrine mode of action)?

The sub-questions are intended to identify adverse effects that are potentially associated with endocrine-mediated modes of action (and to differentiate those that are not).

Participants/population (P)

Humans.

Include: studies in humans, experimental animals, or *in vitro* model systems (mammalian only; studies in which human receptors were expressed in non-mammalian models [and similar such designs] were included) which can be used to assess potential modalities in humans. *in silico* models will be included on a case-by-case basis, depending on relevance of assessed pathway.

Exclude: non-mammalian study models

Exposure(s) (E)

Oxybenzone as a UV filter.

Include: studies with quantitative measures of exposure to oxybenzone, from any route of exposure (e.g., topical, oral gavage, dietary); where appropriate, exposure to oxybenzone via UV filters vs. other sources will be differentiated.

Exclude: Studies evaluating the effects of oxybenzone metabolites or derivatives (and not oxybenzone).

20. Comparator(s)/control (C)

No exposure to oxybenzone (or possibly no/low exposure in observational studies).

Include: Experimental animal and *in vitro* model studies with concurrent untreated or vehicle control; human controlled trials with concurrent negative control.

Include: Human epidemiological studies with a no/low exposure reference group (e.g., bottom quartile of measured serum concentration).

Exclude: studies without a concurrent control or reference group.

Outcome(s) (O)

Estrogenic, androgenic, thyroidal, and steroidogenic (EATS) modalities (i.e. pathways) and potential associations with adverse effects mediated by an endocrine mode of action (as determined by a weight of evidence assessment of the available lines of evidence).

Include: *in vivo* experimental animal and *in vitro* studies which evaluate endpoints that include, but may not be limited to, those in Table 9 from ECHA/EFSA (2018). These endpoints reflect OECD Guideline 150 which lists tests and parameters considered relevant when evaluating endocrine disrupting properties of substances as it relates to EATS modalities.

Include: human studies which evaluate a possible EATS modality or possible adverse outcome associated with ED. Epidemiological literature are included though are generally not designed to measure endpoints such as those described by OECD Guideline 150. Endpoints from epidemiological literature were collected based on expert judgement as selected by SB and represent both possible key events (e.g., hormone levels) as well as potential adverse outcomes (AEs). Inclusion of such studies does not indicate that an AE reported is associated with an endocrine mode of action (rather that is the objective of the current investigation).

Data determined to be important to interpreting the primary outcome, such as toxicokinetic data, will be collected and integrated into the assessment as warranted, but will be regarded as contextual and not included in formal data quality and relevance assessments.

Types/Sources of Studies

Include: peer-reviewed studies, studies reported in authoritative sources (e.g., ECHA Reach Dossiers, NTP CEBS, ToxCast/Tox21) when sufficient information are available to assess study details, quality, and relevance.

Exclude: Reviews, case studies or case series, ecological studies (i.e., no individual assessments of exposure/outcome), conference abstracts, articles not in English.

Evidence Identification (Searches)

Searches will be conducted using PubMed and Embase. Syntax was developed and verified by an information specialist. Searches were validated using key studies identified in previous reviews on similar topics (Ghazipura et al., 2017; Kim and Choi, 2014; Krause et al. 2012).

PubMed search string

(oxybenzone OR benzophenone-3 OR 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzophenone OR oxybenzon OR "131 57 7"[EC/RN Number]) AND ((endocrine OR hormone OR hormones OR estrogen OR estradiol OR anti-estrogen OR estrone OR androgen OR androgeniz* OR

anti-androgen OR testosterone OR “thyroid stimulating hormone” OR thyroxine OR aromatase OR thyroid OR retinoid OR steroidogen* OR TSH OR T3 OR T4 OR triiodothyronine OR gonad OR (receptor AND (binding OR transactivation)) OR reproduct* OR development* OR sperm OR testes OR testis OR ovary OR ovaries OR uterus OR uterine OR vagina* OR adrenals OR adrenal OR (cowper’s AND gland*) OR epididymis OR FSH OR “follicle stimulating hormone” OR “luteinizing hormone” OR “luteinising hormone”) OR “accessory sex organs” OR estrus OR estrous OR “balano-preputial separation” OR anogenital OR cervix OR “coagulating gland” OR genital OR “mammary gland” OR oviduct OR (glans AND penis) OR LABC OR liver OR endometri* OR prostate OR (seminal AND vesicle*) OR “auditory startle” OR fertility OR gestation OR litter OR “motor activity” OR implantation* OR pituitary OR “post-implantation” OR “pre-implantation” OR “sex ratio” OR parturition OR offspring OR pubertal OR puberty OR peripubertal OR neurotox* OR cancer OR carcinogen* OR bioassay OR (repeat* AND dose) OR “28-day” OR “90-day” OR “13-week” OR “one-generation” OR “two-generation” OR uterotrophic OR Hershberger OR toxic OR toxicity OR (adverse AND outcome) OR ecotox* OR zebrafish OR minnow OR medaka OR xenopus OR mammalian OR amphibian OR metamorphosis OR fish OR non-mammalian OR avian OR earthworm OR enchytraeid OR (gonadosomatic AND indexes) OR vitellogenin OR VTG OR spiggin OR “gonado-somatic” OR embryo OR (receptor AND gene AND expression) OR (competitive AND binding)))

Embase search string

((endocrine OR 'hormone'/exp OR hormone OR 'hormones'/exp OR hormones OR 'estrogen'/exp OR estrogen OR 'estradiol'/exp OR estradiol OR 'anti estrogen'/exp OR 'anti estrogen' OR 'estrone'/exp OR estrone OR 'androgen'/exp OR androgen OR androgeniz* OR 'anti androgen'/exp OR 'anti androgen' OR 'testosterone'/exp OR testosterone OR 'thyroid stimulating hormone'/exp OR 'thyroid stimulating hormone' OR 'thyroxine'/exp OR thyroxine OR 'aromatase'/exp OR aromatase OR 'thyroid'/exp OR thyroid OR 'retinoid'/exp OR retinoid OR steroidogen* OR 'tsh'/exp OR tsh OR 't3'/exp OR t3 OR t4 OR 'triiodothyronine'/exp OR triiodothyronine OR 'gonad'/exp OR gonad OR ((('receptor'/exp OR receptor) AND ('binding'/exp OR binding OR 'transactivation'/exp OR transactivation)) OR reproduct* OR development* OR 'sperm'/exp OR sperm OR 'testes'/exp OR testes OR 'testis'/exp OR testis OR 'ovary'/exp OR ovary OR 'ovaries'/exp OR ovaries OR 'uterus'/exp OR uterus OR 'uterine'/exp OR uterine OR vagina* OR 'adrenals'/exp OR adrenals OR 'adrenal'/exp OR adrenal OR (cowper* AND gland*) OR 'epididymis'/exp OR epididymis OR 'fsh'/exp OR fsh OR 'follicle stimulating hormone'/exp OR 'follicle stimulating hormone' OR 'luteinizing hormone'/exp OR 'luteinizing hormone' OR 'luteinising hormone'/exp OR 'luteinising hormone' OR 'accessory sex organs' OR 'estrus'/exp OR estrus OR estrous OR 'balano-preputial separation' OR anogenital OR 'cervix'/exp OR cervix OR 'coagulating gland'/exp OR 'coagulating gland' OR genital OR 'mammary gland'/exp OR 'mammary gland' OR 'oviduct'/exp OR oviduct OR (glans AND ('penis'/exp OR penis)) OR labc OR 'liver'/exp OR liver OR endometri* OR 'prostate'/exp OR prostate OR (seminal AND vesicle*) OR 'auditory startle' OR 'fertility'/exp OR fertility OR 'gestation'/exp OR gestation OR 'litter'/exp OR litter OR 'motor activity'/exp OR 'motor activity' OR implantation* OR 'pituitary'/exp OR pituitary OR 'post-implantation' OR 'pre-

implantation' OR 'sex ratio'/exp OR 'sex ratio' OR 'parturition'/exp OR parturition OR 'offspring'/exp OR offspring OR pubertal OR 'puberty'/exp OR puberty OR peripubertal OR neurotox* OR 'cancer'/exp OR cancer OR carcinogen* OR 'bioassay'/exp OR bioassay OR (repeat* AND ('dose'/exp OR dose)) OR '28-day' OR '90-day' OR '13-week' OR 'one-generation' OR 'two-generation' OR uterotrophic OR hershberger OR toxic* OR (adverse AND ('outcome'/exp OR outcome)) OR ecotox* OR 'zebrafish'/exp OR zebrafish OR 'minnow'/exp OR minnow OR 'medaka'/exp OR medaka OR 'xenopus'/exp OR xenopus OR 'mammalian'/exp OR mammalian OR 'amphibian'/exp OR amphibian OR 'metamorphosis'/exp OR metamorphosis OR 'fish'/exp OR fish OR 'non mammalian' OR 'avian'/exp OR avian OR 'earthworm'/exp OR earthworm OR 'enchytraeid'/exp OR enchytraeid OR (gonadosomatic AND indexes) OR 'vitellogenin'/exp OR vitellogenin OR vtg OR 'spiggin'/exp OR spiggin OR 'gonado-somatic' OR 'embryo'/exp OR embryo OR (('receptor'/exp OR receptor) AND ('gene'/exp OR gene) AND ('expression'/exp OR expression)) OR (competitive AND ('binding'/exp OR binding))) AND ('oxybenzone'/exp OR oxybenzone OR 'benzophenone 3' OR '2 hydroxy 4 methoxybenzophenone' OR oxybenzon OR '131 57 7':rn)) AND [embase]/lim NOT ([embase]/lim AND [medline]/lim)

ToxCast/Tox21

High-throughput screening (HTS) data available through the ToxCast/Tox21 databases were extracted from the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (U.S. EPA) Summary Files database (https://www.epa.gov/chemical-research/toxicity-forecaster-toxcasttm-data;invitrodby_v2); which was released October 2015 and remains the most up-to-date publicly available version that is recommended for use.

Screening and Selection

Following removal of duplicates from PubMed and Embase, studies will be screened by title and abstract (TiAb) using DistillerSR. Subsequently, all studies included following the TiAb will be screened using full text to confirm inclusion.

Data Extraction

Data will be extracted from studies meeting inclusion criteria using templates from EFSA/ECHA (2018). For data that do not conform to such (i.e., ToxCast/Tox21 data, epidemiological data), templates will be developed independently in a manner that is consistent with that from the EFSA/ECHA templates. Additional data relevant to the mode of action assessment as well as the assessment of validity (i.e., reliability and relevance) will also be collected. Data will be extracted based on author report with the exception of fields that may require analyst interpretation (e.g., identification of no or low observed effect levels). Notes will be kept for instances in which data are not sufficiently reported or cases in which underlying data do not support author conclusions (or similar such discrepancies).

Per ECHA/EFSA (2018), outcomes are evaluated based on assessment of the lines of evidence composed of data characterizing endpoints associated with the following categories (levels):

1. Existing data or new non-test information
2. *In vitro* assays providing data about selected endocrine mechanism(s)/pathway(s) (mammalian and non-mammalian methods)
3. *In vivo* assays providing data about selected endocrine mechanism(s)/pathway(s)
4. *In vivo* assays providing data on adverse effects on endocrine relevant endpoints
5. *In vivo* assays providing more comprehensive data on adverse effects on endocrine relevant endpoints over more extensive parts of the life cycle of the organism

Data will be extracted via templates such that the level of the assay is categorized, thus facilitating integration.

Assessment of Reliability and Relevance

Internal validity, herein used as a measure of the reliability (per EFSA/ECHA), will be assessed by study type:

- *In vivo* experimental animal studies: OHAT Risk of Bias Tool (2015) and/or SciRAP Tool for *in vivo* studies
- *In vitro* studies: Klimisch (1997) and/or SciRAP Tool for *in vitro* studies
- Epidemiological data: OHAT Risk of Bias Tool

Multiple tools will be considered in order to facilitate integration of data and comparison of internal validity. For all tools, criteria will be refined based on topic area and piloted prior to appraisal. Utilization of a positive control in appropriate assays will be considered as important in determining validity, as will considerations of cytotoxicity and maximum tolerated dose.

Relevance will be assessed both at the level of inclusion/exclusion (based on relevance to the PECO) as well as via the categorization of studies by level per EFSA/ECHA (2018).

Synthesis and Integration

Per ECHA/EFSA (2018) guidance, which is similar that used by the USEPA but not described per a guideline, relevant data will be compiled and synthesized for E, A, T, S modalities separately. The potential for activity and adversity will subsequently be assessed within each line of evidence. Effects that occur in the presence of overt toxicity will not be included in the assessment. Per EFSA/ECHA guidance, data from epidemiological studies will be integrated on a case-by-case basis pending applicability to the relevant lines of evidence or characterization of potential adverse outcomes. A variety of tools (tables, figures, and other visualizations) will facilitate an objective and qualitative synthesis of the available data. Data relevance and reliability (including risk of bias and other

measurements of validity) will be characterized both at individual study level as well as considered when assessing each line of evidence as part of integration.

For human studies (for which the ECHA/EFSA guidance does not specifically describe a process for including), evidence analysts will use a weight of evidence approach incorporating concepts such as consistency, dose response, imprecision, indirectness, magnitude of effect, confounding, publication bias, and other threats to validity to characterize confidence in individual studies as well as the body of literature. Analytical tools, such as funnel plots or weight function models, may be used to evaluate publication bias.

All evidence (i.e., both positive and negative) of sufficient reliability will be integrated using a stepwise weight of evidence approach. First, an initial analysis of the evidence will be conducted to determine whether there is sufficient empirical support for activity and adversity for each line of evidence. Within EPA's and most recently ECHA/EFSA WoE approach, data is considered as lines of evidence extracted from guideline type studies and studies determined to provide mechanistic changes in vivo or in vitro that are both scientifically and biologically relevant with regard to chemical treatment related effect. Specifically, a hypothesis-driven weight-of-evidence (WoE) analysis will be conducted based on the ranking of endocrine endpoints from Level 1 to Level 5 studies across eight endocrine hypotheses (Borgert et al., 2014). These eight hypotheses include evaluating the potential of BP-3 to act as (1) an estrogen agonist, (2) an estrogen antagonist, (3) an androgen agonist, (4) an androgen antagonist, (5) a thyroid agonist, (6) a thyroid antagonist, (7) an inducer of steroidogenesis, and/or (8) an inhibitor of steroidogenesis.

Should such activity be determined by pathway (and direction; agonism/antagonism), the second analysis will involve a mode of action analysis to establish if there is a link between the adverse effect(s) and the endocrine activity. The weight of the evidence analysis will involve evaluation of the mode of action as part of an adverse outcome pathway, with particular emphasis on biological plausibility for concordance of key events and key event relationship (and if such is supported by the empirical data). Expert judgement will be necessary when considering the available lines of evidence, including the overall evaluation of consistency, magnitude, dose relevance, and dose-response (OHAT, 2015). Data gaps and uncertainties will be identified and the impact of such characterized based.

Conclusions will be developed based on considerations of the mode of action relative to human use of oxybenzone in UV filters (e.g., sunscreen). Conclusions will be characterized by 1) discussion of key studies; 2) description of inconsistent or conflicting data; 3) overall strength of evidence supporting a conclusion; and, 4) uncertainties and their potential impact to conclusions (as well as identification of what, if any, data are needed and why).

If data are amenable, quantitative analyses (such as meta-analyses or meta-regression) will be considered.

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